

POTENTIOMETRIC ESTIMATION OF LEAD WITH SULPHIDE SOLUTIONS.

BY GOPAL LAL MAHESHWARI AND J. B. JHA.

Lead has been potentiometrically estimated by several methods; Muller and Gabler (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1922, **62**, 28) used ferriferrocyanide electrode for its determination. The method is said to give good results for concentrations above 0.01M. This electrode has been investigated by Muller in collaboration with various authors for the titrations of lead in presence of various metals. Many of these methods require very precise conditions for successful results and hence their utility as working methods is limited. (Muller and Pree, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1927, **72**, 200; also Muller and Hentschel *ibid.*, 1927, **72**, 1). More recently Pamfilov and Ivanoeva (*J. Gen. Chem.*, 1931, **1**, 760) have used what they term bromopotentiometric method. Gelbachadd and Compton (*Ing. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1930, **2**, 397) have described a method with the use of thermionic valves. These authors have used potassium chromate solutions as the precipitant and the end-point is denoted by a minimum deflection on a milliammeter. Kolthoff and Furman ('Potentiometric Titrations,' 1931, p. 187) have described a method with the use of sodium sulphide as precipitant and silver in 1.5N-KBr as a compensation electrode. The error in this case amounted to 1—2%.

Recently Mukai (*Bull. Tech. Coll. Kyushu Imp. Univ.*, 1929, **4**, 17) has applied the principle of the potentiometric titrations to the estimation of lead. Good results have been obtained with lead nitrate solutions only; with lead acetate solutions the results are irregular. Millet (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1929, **25**, 147) has also shown that the concentrations of lead ions can be obtained by the E.M.F. measurements of lead in lead citrate solutions but his aim is not analytical as is evident from the perusal of his paper.

The titrations described below were carried out with hydrogen sulphide solutions and the method has the merit of being more accurate and simple. The whole titration can be performed within a few minutes, without the use of any mechanical device for stirring, etc. The method, however, is not suitable for solutions having concentrations greater than 0.02N, as it has been found difficult to increase the concentration of hydrogen sulphide for corresponding titrations. Moreover, hydrogen sulphide requires care in keeping and have to be standardised daily. The standardisation is not difficult and can be carried out with standard iodine solutions.

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

Lead Solutions.—Lead in the form of lead acetate dissolved in water with a little acetic acid to get a clear solution was used for estimation. To check the results of titrations lead was estimated gravimetrically as sulphate.

Sulphide Solutions.—These were prepared from sodium sulphide (B. D. H. A. R.) by dissolving it in a buffer solution consisting of equal volumes of sodium acetate and acetic acid solutions each 0.2*N*. The hydrogen sulphide solution was kept under hydrogen and used in the same way as titanous chloride solutions are used in reduction methods of titrations (Knecht and Hibbert, "Reduction Methods of Titration," 2nd Edition).

It may be pointed out here that the solutions keep admirably well under hydrogen. Photochemical action on the decomposition of hydrogen sulphide of the surface action due to glass seems to be slow. In one case no measurable change was observed after 30 hours.

Titration Vessel.—A special titration vessel was made out of a wide-mouthed bottle. A cork with three holes was fitted to the mouth of the bottle (250 c.c.). Platinum electrode, the connecting end of the calomel electrode and the lower end of the burette were inserted into these holes. A closed bottle for the titrations is necessary to check the loss due to diffusion, while the solution is flowing out of the burette.

The hydrogen sulphide solution was standardised by running out a known volume of the solution from the burette in a standard iodine solution containing a known amount of iodine. The excess of iodine was then titrated back with sodium thiosulphate solution of known strength.

The agreement between gravimetric and potentiometric results is given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Conc. of lead acetate soln. (approx.).	Conc. of H ₂ S soln. used (approx.).	Pb in lead acetate soln. found by gravimetric analysis (g./25 c.c.)	Pb found by potentiometric titration (g./25 c.c.)	Percentage error.
M/40	M/66	0.1054	0.1053	0.09
M/60	M/66	0.07645	0.0765	0.07
M/100	M/66	0.046915	0.04691	0.1
M/140	M/56	0.03416	0.03498	0.1
M/200	M/100	0.023457	0.023457	0.0
M/240	M/100	0.019114	0.01212	0.03
M/280	M/100	0.01708	0.01710	0.1
M/500	M/250	0.009380	0.009383	0.0
M/700	M/250	0.006832	0.006832	0.0
M/2000	M/250	0.002345	0.002345	0.0

E. M. F. variations during two titrations are given below.

The titrations were carried with a drop burette as suggested by Kolthoff and Furman ("Potentiometric Titrations," 1934, p. 84).

Concentrated solutions of lead acetate were prepared and the amount of lead estimated by the gravimetric method as sulphate. The solution was then diluted to the strengths (approximate) given below.

TABLE II.

Lead acetate = $M/500$ (approx.)

Vol. of H_2S solution.	Pb pptd.	E. M. F. in volts against saturated calomel electrode.
0 c.c.	0.0%	-0.0400 volt.
5	76.55	-0.0210
6	91.66	-0.0380
6.112	...	-0.0450
6.224	95.3	-0.0300
6.336	...	-9.0590
6.382	...	-0.0650
6.45	...	-0.0750
6.50	99.58	-9.1000
6.55	...	-0.1450
6.60	101.3	-0.1720

Maximum = $\frac{de}{dc}$ at 6.53 c.c.

Quantity of lead found by potentiometric titration = 0.009383 g./25 c.c.

Quantity of lead found by gravimetric analysis = 0.009313 g./25 c.c.

Percentage error = 0%.

TABLE III

Lead acetate = $M/2000$ (approx.)

Vol. of H_2S soln.	Pb pptd.	E. M. F. against saturated calomel electrode.
0 c.c.	0%	+0.0520 volt.
3	69.2	-0.0040
9	77.92	-0.0120
10	86.58	-0.0170
11	95.24	-0.0300
11.2	96.97	-0.0420
11.3	...	-0.0580
11.4	...	-0.0680
11.46	...	-0.0740
11.51	99.59	-0.0900
11.55	...	-0.1400
11.60	100.45	-0.1550

Maximum $\frac{de}{dc}$ at 11.535 c. c.

Amount of lead found by the above titration = 0.002345 g./25c.c.

Amount of lead found by the gravimetric analysis = 0.002345 g./25c.c.

Percentage error = 0%

It is clear from the above table that the method gives better results for more dilute solutions than for stronger ones.

The method is specially adopted for the estimation of lead in lead acetate solutions used in dyeing industry, where estimations are frequently required and are done with more tedious methods.

S U M M A R Y .

Potentiometric titration of lead with hydrogen sulphide solution has been described. The results have been found to be satisfactory for dilute solutions of lead acetate.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
AGRA COLLEGE, AGRA.

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